

PHENOLIC COMPOUNDS OF PLANTS BELONGING TO THE GENUS**ATRAPHAXIS****Yulchiyeva U.A.****Abdullayev Sh.V.****N.G'. Abdulladjonova**

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At present, the isolation of biologically active substances from plants, the comprehensive study of their chemical structure and properties, as well as the investigation of their biological and pharmacological characteristics, is one of the urgent tasks. Phenolic compounds, which are widespread in the plant kingdom, represent a large class of natural compounds. Phenolic compounds participate in various processes occurring in the human body and exhibit antioxidant properties; moreover, as antiradical agents, they slow down radical mechanism-based reactions that take place in the organism under the influence of external physico-chemical factors. It has been established that phenolic compounds in the human body enhance immunity against diseases caused by bacteria and viruses and possess therapeutic properties. In particular, carbohydrates, macro- and microelements, vitamins, hydrolyzable tannins, flavonoids, organic acids, and other classes of compounds have been isolated from plants of the genus *Atraphaxis* belonging to the family *Polygonaceae*, and on their basis, medicinal preparations with effective biological activity are widely used in medical practice. Species of the genus *Atraphaxis* are mainly highly branched shrubs and subshrubs that grow in arid zones of temperate steppe and desert regions of Central Asia, America, and Australia. Below, we will discuss the medicinal properties of certain plants belonging to this family:

Atraphaxis frutescens- (Iran, Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan) — in alleviating stomach and digestive disorders;

Atraphaxis pyrifolia- (Iran, Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan) — in the treatment of diseases, asthma, cough, various wounds, and skin inflammations;

Atraphaxis brinaludensis- (Iran, Kazakhstan) — in reducing inflammation in arthritis, in the treatment of joint pain, and in skin inflammations;

Atraphaxis spinosa- (Algeria, Uzbekistan) — in treating stomach-related disorders and diseases affecting intestinal health;

Atraphaxis seravschanica- (Turkmenistan, Tajikistan) — found to be used in wound healing and in the treatment of skin inflammations.

For the first time, the chemical composition of the aerial parts of *Atraphaxis pyrifolia*, a species of the genus *Atraphaxis* growing in the Tashkent region, has been studied.

In the study of the polyphenols in its composition, the aerial parts of the plant were first collected and dried in a cool place. Two hundred grams of the plant material were weighed, and three successive extractions were carried out at room temperature for 24 hours each with 70% acetone at a 1:5 ratio. The acetone extracts were filtered and concentrated using a rotary evaporator at 50 °C. The concentrated extract was fractionated with ethyl acetate. The ethyl acetate fraction obtained was evaporated using a rotary evaporator at 30 °C. The resulting concentrate was precipitated with chloroform.

Flavonoids	<i>Atraphaxis pyrifolia</i>
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	Concentration (mg/g)
Dihydroquercetin	10.63
Rutin	28.71
Quercetin	3.84
Salidroside	5.94
Rozavin	21.61

When the total polyphenolic composition was analyzed using High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC) with standard compounds, it was established that the aerial parts of *Atraphaxis pyrifolia* contain the polyphenols rutin, dihydroquercetin, quercetin, salidroside, and rosavin. The HPLC results indicate that the sufficient presence of the flavonoids rutin, rosavin, and dihydroquercetin in *Atraphaxis pyrifolia* reveals promising prospects for the development of pharmaceuticals and biologically active supplements (BAS) based on this plant.